

Investigate the Economic Performance, Per Capita GDP, Energy Consumption, Domestic Product and Trade Openness on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan

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Abstract

This thesis aims to study the effect of Economic Performance, Per Capita GDP, energy consumption, and trade openness on carbon emissions in Pakistan during the period 1990-2019. The importance of analyzing the effect of these factors on CO₂ (carbon dioxide) emissions, also known as "greenhouse gases emissions", stems from the underlying danger of these emissions. Recently, the negative effects of these emissions on climate change have become a hot topic around the world. More alarmingly, the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP, 2014) has announced that global temperature has increased by two degrees Celsius, these changes might be irreversible.

Pakistan was one of the first countries that took actions regarding the subject of the impact of carbon emissions. Pakistan signed the climate change agreement in 1992, and ratified the Kyoto Protocol in 1997. Pakistan's second report on the climate change for 2000 mentioned that the total greenhouse gas emissions are equivalent to 20 million tons of carbon dioxide. The energy sector, which accounted to about 27% of these emissions, takes lead. It is closely followed by the transport sector which accounted to about 20%. The third most influential sector is the waste sector which accounted for about 13% of the emissions tracking the timeline of GDP shows CO₂ emissions have taken an upward trend during the period of 1990-2019, except for the period between 1988 and 1991 where GDP level declined as a result of the economic crisis to the Pakistani economy which was a result of the deterioration of exchange rate during that period.

Findings also indicate that a per capita carbon emission have a positive relationship with foreign trade to GDP ratio and with energy consumption, while Economic Performance, has a negative and significant impact on per capita carbon emissions in the long- run. The results also support the validity of EKC hypothesis in Pakistan's economy, which means that the level of CO₂ emissions in Pakistan increases with Per Capita GDP during the initial stage, continues until a stabilization point, and then emissions start declining. Moreover, using error-correction depending on the Granger causality test, the study finds a causal relationship between the variables. In particularly, there exists a unidirectional long-run causality from per capita GDP, the square of per capita GDP, per capita energy use and Economic Performance to per capita carbon emissions.

Keywords: Economic Performance, Per Capita GDP, Energy Consumption, Domestic Product, Trade Openness, Carbon Emissions

1.1 Introduction

Since last two decades protection of the environment became a top economic and social priority across the globe. This vision has been adopted by many international organizations including the United Nations, which established a specialized body called the "United Nations Environment Programme". The first Conference on Environment was held in Stockholm in 1972 as an attempt to study and address the relationship between the environment and development at the global level. After that, many seminars and conferences were held, and the most important conference called "The Earth Summit" was held in 1992.

The travel industry is viewed as supportive in boosting the world economies by making new openings and opening new territories for venture, however it likewise put ecological weight by emanating tremendous measure of CO₂ emissions as it includes high energy utilization because of transport, air travel and food. In this way, it is expressed that being development well disposed, the travel industry could be unsafe to ecological quality (Shi et al., 2019).

Essentially, Sharif et al. (2017) examined that there is single direction causality running from the travel industry to CO₂ emissions. Raza et al. (2017) confirmed the connection among the travel industry and CO₂ outflows in the United States. The outcomes uncovered that travel industry is a segment of CO₂ outflows

and it unidirectional can cause CO₂ discharges. In addition, on account of China, Chen et al. (2018) featured that the development in the travel industry influences CO₂ emanations and the vehicle area is the primary factor in CO₂ discharges during 2001–2015.

Outflows of carbon dioxide have as of late been viewed as a significant issue universally, because of the negative impact of these emanations on atmosphere changes. Atmosphere changes incorporate changing precipitation designs, an expansion the force of tempests, an inversion in seas flows, and rising ocean levels. These progressions impactfully affect biological systems, and the endurance of natural life and prosperity of mankind (Boutabba, 2013).

In the retail field, where an ever increasing number of players rival each other, buyers experience each day with a wide assortment of item data, provided through bundling, marking or promoting. Data, for example, taste, item configuration, brand name, guarantee or nation of source can assume significant parts in buyer assessments of items (Balabanis and Diamantopoulos, 2004). Perhaps the most established worry of retailing and customer administrations is whether the "unfamiliarity" marking of an item will make it pretty much desirable over buyers in various nations (Verlegh and Steenkamp, 1999). A broad corpus of writing has detailed that a predisposition against unfamiliar items and for homegrown ones does, indeed, exist (Lin and Chen, 2006; Sharma, 2011).

During the development cycle, the biological nature of any country debases quickly because of abatement in backwoods cover, disintegration of surrounding air quality, and soil disintegration (Destek and Sinha 2020). Generally, toxins like carbon dioxide (CO₂) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) discharges are considered as the natural or ecological pointers. Notwithstanding, for the pointer of natural quality, we have chosen environmental impression. There is an enduring conversation about the determination of biological impression as a natural pointer (Templett 2000; Kissinger and Haim 2008; Wiedmann and Barrett 2010; Moore et al. 2013; Galli 2015). Biological impression clarifies the conveying limit of the aggregate region of the environment to create the assets which are devoured by the financial cycle, and furthermore shows the capacity to retain the produced squander (Wackernagel et al. 1999; Solis-Guzman and Marrero 2015; Peng et al. 2019).

There are two primary purposes behind choosing natural impression as a pointer of ecological quality. In the first place, it speaks to the conveying limit of the earth, and thus, a superior estimation gadget for the supportability of environmental framework with contrast with poisons. As per Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the environmental impression is the main instrument which thinks about the natural and organic capacity of earth for practical financial exercises and advancement (Rashid et al. 2018; Nazar et al. 2018; Pan et al. 2019). Second, characteristic assets (water, minerals, land assets, and woods) are devoured because of monetary exercises. Thus, in the event that emanations are picked as natural pointers, at that point they will overlook the biological supportability just as the huge human and modern exercises which can harm the manageability of the environment (Li et al. 2019).

This instrument includes new and effective advances and imaginative cycles which eventually decrease the extreme utilization of non-sustainable power assets, hence, assumes a significant function in natural front. It is contended that underlying changes lead to changes in the creation, piece of buyer interest, asset use, global exchange and financial components of the economy. Hence, this investigation without precedent for the instance of Pakistan, following crafted by Ali et al. (2017) on account of Malaysia, under the underlying change speculation and Lewis' Structural Changes hypothesis, centers around the part of primary changes close by the travel industry and monetary development in deciding the CO₂ discharges. Since move from more energy-concentrated assembling area towards more administrations based and less energy-escalated area (the travel industry) could prompt diminishing the utilization of energy in gainful exercises in the nation, thusly, the effect of decreased energy use is likewise critical to be examined in natural viewpoint.

Because of the significance of carbon outflows' issue, this investigation means to examine the impacts of Economic Performance, Per Capita, Energy Consumption, Domestic Product and Trade Openness on Carbon Emissions. This will be finished by noting the accompanying issues: Investigate the Economic Performance and carbon emanations in Pakistan changed over the period (1990-2019). Examine the effect of Energy Consumption, Domestic Product and Trade Openness on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan. Examine natural Kuznets bend accomplished in Pakistan.

Research Questions

- Does Economic Performance effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan positively or negatively?
- Does Per Capita effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan positively or negatively?
- Does Energy Consumption effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan positively or negatively?
- Does Domestic Product effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan positively or negatively?
- Does Trade Openness effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan positively or negatively?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the impact of financial development and other variables on carbon emissions. Moreover, the specific goals to be achieved are:

1. To observing the change in Economic Performance in Pakistan over the period (1990-2019).
2. To identify the association of Economic Performance on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan.
3. To study the relationship of Per Capita effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan.
4. To identify the association of Energy Consumption effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan.
5. To study of Domestic Product effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan.
6. To study the relationship of Trade Openness effect on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan.

Theoretical Framework

Literature Review

CO2 emissions have been considered by many researchers. Most of these studies have attempted to identify the factors which influence CO2 emissions and their level, as well as the direction of their influence. The most prominent variables which were found to influence carbon emissions were Economic Performance, economic growth, trade openness, and energy consumption. Below, the study provides a review of literature on these variables.

A considerable lot of the investigations utilized the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) testing methodology (Boutabba, 2013; Ozturk and Acaravci, 2013; Jalil and Feridun, 2011; Shahbaz et al., 2011; Zhang, 2011; Tamazian et al., 2009; Sadorsky, 2010). Moreover, a few examinations utilized the co-reconciliation hypothesis, vector mistake rectification displaying methods, Granger causality test, and fluctuation decay (Zhang, 2011; Menyah and Wolde-Rufael, 2010; Soytas and Sari, 2009; Ang, 2007).

Among the factors inspected, monetary improvement was by a wide margin the most well known. Utilizing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) testing methods, just as, the ARDL bound testing strategy and utilized co-joining hypothesis, vector blunder amendment demonstrating procedures, Granger causality test, Ozturk and Acaravci (2013) analyze the connection between carbon outflow, monetary turn of events, financial development, energy utilization and exchange receptiveness Turkey from 1960 to 2007. Utilizing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound testing strategy. They utilize the homegrown acknowledge to private area as pointer of monetary turn of events. Directing an investigation in Turkey which showed that monetary advancement has no critical impact on CO2 emanations. Notwithstanding,

numerous other indicated that monetary advancement without a doubt has a huge relationship with CO2 outflows.

Economic Performance

Monetary execution is perceived with regards to this examination as securities exchange based proportions of monetary return. Securities exchange based measures are desirable over bookkeeping based measures, as the last are more influenced by administrative caution in the use of bookkeeping rules or by times of elevated expansion and depend on past information, while securities exchange based measures are forward-glancing in that they depend on future anticipated execution (Johnson and Kaplan, 1987; Venkatraman and Ramanujam, 1986; Schipper, 1989). Besides it should be recognized that monetary danger (again estimated either by bookkeeping or securities exchange based) is an extra viewpoint to be considered in surveying the connection among manageability and financial execution in a more thorough way (Orlitzky and Benjamin, 2001).

Expanding on archetypes of the examinations talked about above, McWilliams and Siegel (2000) have contended that excluded variable predisposition happens if R&D and publicizing forces are not considered as an indicator for monetary execution. They contend that this is on the grounds that the market estimation of a firm can be isolated into its substantial resource esteem (assessed from bookkeeping esteems and substitution expenses) and its elusive resource esteem (licenses, brand names, exclusive crude material sources, brand/name notoriety and firm generosity). The immaterial resource esteem in these fundamentally relies upon publicizing and R&D uses comparative with deals (Scholtens, 2008).

Per Capita

MacCulloch infers that GDP per capita development by 1,600 US dollars (in 2001 costs) decreases the danger of the dispersal of progressive thoughts by 2.4%, while the extent of individuals who might want to make an unrest is diminished by 41% (MacCulloch, 2004). MacCulloch and Pezzini (2010) utilize the miniature information of the studies of progressive inclinations of 130,000 individuals from 61 nations during 1980-1997. State's having a place with the medium quintile in GDP per capita end up being a measurably huge indicator of socio-political destabilization of the "focal breakdown" design (Korotayev, Issaev, and Vasiliev, 2015; Korotayev, Issaev, and Zinkina, 2015).

Regardless of the utilization of different contamination markers and control factors through multivariate or bivariate relapse models, observational proof has stayed uncertain. Furthermore, writing on the EKC speculation typically centers around CO2emissions, which may prompt misleading assessments because of the way that the blend of gushing has moved from sulfur and nitrogen oxides to carbon dioxide and strong waste, causing total carbon discharges to show an upward pattern (Ulucak and Bilgili, 2018). The way that CO2 emanations will in general be upward moved represents an issue for those examinations that attention on CO2 outflows in their investigation of the EKC theory as it can inclination the appraisals. Following this understanding, financial analysts ought to research the EKC theory by considering a more comprehensive natural debasement marker, for example, the per capita EF. Thirdly, writing depends on various econometric methodologies coming from early examinations utilizing time arrangement models to ongoing experimental investigations dependent on board information relapse models. A few researchers have introduced the benefits and negative marks of various econometric methodologies utilized in EKC writing (Narayan et al., 2016).

Energy Consumption

The causal connection between energy utilization and pay is an all-around considered theme in the writing of energy financial matters. The causality is in the feeling of Granger causality Granger, 1969 , Kraft and Kraft 1978 , in their spearheading study, discovered $\check{Z} \rightarrow \check{Z}$ unidirectional causality running from GNP to energy utilization for the United States. They used the method of Sims 1972 and utilized yearly information for the $\check{Z}$. 1947-1974 period. In any case, Akarca and Long 1980 called attention to that the KraftKraft results are false by changing the time span by 2 years. Different investigations using diverse time-frames and various methods have either affirmed or repudiated KraftKraft results Abosedra and Baghestani, 1989; Yu $\check{Z}$ and Choi, 1985; Cheng, 1995; Hwang and Gum, 1991; Erol and Yu, 1987.. The huge number of studies around there, tragically, discovered various outcomes for various nations just as for various time

spans inside a similar nation. In latest examinations, specialists have zeroed in on the cointegrating connection between energy utilization and pay for a couple of nations for example Yu and Jin, Ž 1992; Masih and Masih, 1996, 1997; Glasure and Lee, 1997.

Then again, Ali, Abdullah et al. (2016, Ali, Azrai et al. 2017) on account of Malaysia inferred that energy utilization and financial development are significant pointers of CO₂ outflows within the sight of monetary development and primary changes in the economy. Additionally, on account of Pakistan, Liu et al. (2019) inspected the dynamic connection between CO₂ outflows, worldwide the travel industry and energy utilization alongside other control factors and inferred that monetary development alongside energy utilization are the primary indications of an expansion in CO₂ discharges.

Domestic Product

In the retail field, where an ever increasing number of players rival each other, customers experience each day with a wide assortment of item data, provided through bundling, marking or publicizing. Data, for example, taste, item configuration, brand name, guarantee or nation of inception can assume significant functions in purchaser assessments of items (Balabanis and Diamantopoulos, 2004). Perhaps the most seasoned worry of retailing and customer administrations is whether the "unfamiliarity" marking of an item will make it pretty much desirable over purchasers in various nations (Verlegh and Steenkamp, 1999). A broad corpus of writing has announced that an inclination against unfamiliar items and for homegrown ones does, truth be told, exist (Lin and Chen, 2006; Sharma, 2011).

Buyer ethnocentrism (hereafter CE), which alludes to the propensity of shoppers to see homegrown items as better than unfamiliar other options (Cheah et al., 2016; Shimp and Sharma, 1987), is grounded in the conviction that it isn't all in all correct to buy unfamiliar made products as it might hurt homegrown economy or incite work misfortune (Chan et al., 2010; Siamagka and Balabanis, 2015). As revealed by Siamagka and Balabanis (2015), some notable worldwide firms, for example, Walmart (USA) or Marks & Spencers (UK) have even misused ethnocentrism by dispatching "purchase homegrown" limited time crusades with the plan to safeguard public characters and appeal to ethnocentric customers.

Trade Openness

Exchange receptiveness influences natural quality adversely or decidedly by different channels as indicated by the degree of industrialization and globalization in an economy (Raza et al. 2017; Destek and Sinha 2020). As indicated by the contamination have theory (PHH), a host economy with careless or good-for-nothing climate permits gets dirtier with exchange openness (Copeland and Taylor 1994; Talukdar and Meisner 2001; Hoffman et al. 2005; He 2006; Baek and Koo 2009). Grossman and Krueger (1991) and Antweiler et al. (2001) made a comprehensive effort to clarify the impacts of exchange receptiveness on the ecological quality and decayed these impacts in to scale impact, procedure impact, and organization impact. The creation impact of exchange receptiveness mirrors an adjustment in the constituents of a nation's yield when it opens up to exchange and turns out to be more globalized. On the off chance that near preferences of a nation are arranged to clean ventures, at that point exchange transparency will prompt a move from dirtied or filthy products to less contaminated or clean merchandise and enterprises. It is seen that the creation cycle of filthy merchandise is capital-escalated while the yield of clean products is more human resources concentrated or work r-serious. On the off chance that the size of creation and different components stay consistent, a nation that moves its yield towards capital-serious items will make more contamination, while a nation that moves its creation towards work escalated items or away from capital-concentrated items will produce less contamination (Grossman and Krueger 1991; Cole and Elliott 2003; Shao et al. 2019).

Carbon Emissions

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Data and Methodology:

data collection method, population and sampling, measures and data analysis are discussed. As there are three approaches used in methodology but in our research method in this study use quantitative based approach. Positivism paradigm used in this quantitative based study. As this paradigm is formal language used in this study. In quantitative study we will use deduction process.

In this study picked positivism research worldview as study will do explore confirmation with derivation technique in which this research will likewise check circumstances and logical results relationship of factors. So in such case positivism technique is a lot of appropriate for this sort of overview and examination work. Present investigation comprises on positivism paradigm to discover the relationship were planned and quantitative methodology utilized. What's more, the information is positivist in nature so the worldview will be positivism. In this worldview hypothesis is confirmed based on speculation.

Research approach used here is quantitative as well as deduction research approach.

The group of people, we selected for the collection of data and become the part of survey for the research known as population.

To accomplish the past goals, the examination utilizes econometric investigation to look at the since quite a while ago run balance, the presence and the course of a causal connection between Economic Performance, Square of Per Capita, Energy Consumption, Domestic Product and Trade Openness on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan. In especially, the examination utilizes the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) limits testing methodology, unit root test and Granger Causality test to investigate such connections.

The examination utilizes time-arrangement information for the period (1990-2019), got from the Stat Bank information bases.

3.1.6 Methodology and Data

The objective of this article is to analyze the effects of Economic Performance, Square of Per Capita, Energy Consumption, Domestic Product and Trade Openness on Carbon Emissions in Pakistan". Following the empirical literature Boutabba, 2013; Ozturk and Acaravci, 2013; Jalil and Feridun, 2011; Shahbaz et al., 2011; Soytaş et al., 2007; Ang, 2007, the relationship between dependent and independent variables can be expressed as the following:

$$CO_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1 P + \beta_2 Y^2 + \beta_3 E + \beta_4 D + \beta_5 T + \epsilon_t$$

Where CO_2 is carbon outflow (estimated in Kilo tone), P demonstrates financial execution (estimated in nearby steady money), Y^2 is the square of monetary execution, E is the energy utilization (estimated as kg of oil same), D is the Domestic Product that is the all-out estimation of homegrown acknowledge to private area as a portion of financial execution, and T speaks to exchange receptiveness, which is the absolute estimation of fares and imports as a portion of monetary execution. These factors were gotten from the Stat Bank, while, exchange transparency, which takes from the Stat Bank information base.

The boundaries β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , and β_5 are the drawn out flexibility of CO_2 outflows concerning monetary execution, the squared monetary presentation, energy use, monetary turn of events and exchange receptiveness individually. The indication of β_1 is relied upon to be positive. Under the EKC theory, a negative sign is normal for β_2 . The factual unimportance of β_2 suggests a monotonic addition in the connection between poison outflows and financial execution. This can likewise be clarified as follows: β_1 being positive reveals the wonder where the CO_2 discharges increment pay increments too. β_2 being

negative mirrors the reversed U formed example of the EKC, where once pay passes the limit, the CO2 emanations will diminish.

Unit Root Tests

As contended before, the ARDL limits testing method can be applied whether or not the factors are I (0), I (1) or partially co-incorporated (Pesaran and Pesaran, 1997). Be that as it may, as per Ouattara (2004), in the presence of I (2) factors the figured F-measurements gave by Pesaran et al. (2001) become invalid. Therefore, the execution of unit root tests in the ARDL strategy is critical to ensure that none of the factors is coordinated at a request for I (2) or past. For this reason, this investigation utilizes the customary Augmented Dicky Fuller (ADF) tests. The invalid speculation expresses that there exist unit roots. Conversely, the elective speculation expresses that there is no unit root (the arrangement is writing material). The Dickey Fuller relapses remember a catch for the levels, and remember a block for the main contrasts. We tried every factor for a unit root at the 5 percent levels of centrality.

4.1.2 According to the unit-root test, table (1)

Shows that the null hypothesis is not rejected, meaning that the variables are non-stationary, hence, all variables have unit root test. This is because the absolute value of the t-statistics is lower than the MacKinnon (or ADF) critical value at 5% level of significance, in other words, t-statistics < critical value at 5% level of significance.

Table 1: ADF Test at Levels (at Intercept)

Variables	t-statistics	Critical value at 5%
CO2	0.796	-2.986
P	-0.262	-2.971
Y ²	-0.233	-2.971
E	-0.824	-2.967
D	-0.976	-2.986
T	0.652	-2.957

In the contrary, table (2) shows that all variable under study are stationary at first difference, where the t-statistics are higher than the MacKinnon (or ADF) critical value at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that all series are I (1), because they became stationary at first difference.

Table 2: ADF Test at First Difference (at Intercept)

Variable	t-statistics	Critical value at 5%
CO2	-3.67	-2.981
P	-3.67	-2.967
Y ²	-3.31	-2.967
E	-6.24	-2.982
D	-5.06	-2.960
T	-3.11	-2.960

Co-integration Test Results

The co- integration test requires that the variables under consideration are not integrated at an order higher than one. Based on the Akaike Information (AIC) and the Schwarz–Bayesian criteria (SBC) information, the optimal number of lags of the model is selected as suggested by Pesaran et al. (2001). The results of these criteria show that the optimal number of lags is one.

Table (3)

Presents the calculated F-statistics, together with the critical values, are reported in Table 3. The F-test has a non-standard distribution that depends on four factors: the order of variables included in the ARDL model, the number of explanatory variables, whether the ARDL model includes an intercept and time trend, and the sample size.

Long run and Short-run Elasticity’s

Given the presence of a long-run relationship, the ARDL co-integration procedure was implemented to estimate Eq. (2) with maximum order of lag set to 1. The AIC criterion has been used to determine the

coefficients of the level variables. As AIC is a good criterion, since it selects the smallest possible lag length and minimizes the loss of degree of freedoms as well. The long-run results are reported in table 4, where all estimated coefficients are statistically significant at 5% level of significance.

Table 4: Long-run Estimation Results (of CO2 Emissions)

Regressor	Coefficient
P	9.113957*** (3.097399)
Y ²	-0.605954*** (0.204776)
E	0.453831*** (0.226475)
D	-0.798910*** (0.331434)
T	0.216487*** (0.103545)
Constant	40.58031*** (12.94523)

Note: The asterisks *** is 5% significant level. The numbers in parentheses are standard error.

Under the EKC speculation, the since quite a while ago run versatility of Economic Performance carbon discharges as for Economic Performance and the per capita pay expected to be $\beta_1 > 0$ and $\beta_2 < 0$ separately. This infers that both direct and non-straight terms of GDP give verification in help to rearranged U formed connection between financial development and CO₂emissions. According to capita GDP increments, per capita carbon discharges increment also, until some edge level of per capita GDP is accomplished, at that point carbon emanations start to decrease. In particular, results show that a 1% ascent in GDP will raise CO₂emissions by 9.11%. These confirmations uphold the EKC theory, uncovering the way that CO₂ outflows increment in the underlying phase of financial development however decrease after a limit point. This finding is reliable with the aftereffect of [Agras et al.(1999), Fodha and Zaghdoud (2010), Song et al.(2008), Halicioglu (2009), Lean and Smyth (2010) and Ozturk and Acaravci (2013) and Shahbaz et al. (2012)].

Table 5: Short-run Estimation Results (of CO2 Emissions)

Regressor	Coefficient
ΔP	2.208797 (2.899412)
ΔY^2	-0.146064 (0.190980)
ΔE	-0.145191 (0.317566)
ΔD	0.310848 (0.185944)
ΔT	-0.117686 (0.110484)
Δ constant	0.022499 (0.014702)
ECM(-1)	-0.507775** (0.146489)
R ²	0.4926
S.E of regression	0.0540
S.E of regression	0.0540
Diagnostic test	P-value
Serial correlation LM Test	0.6811
Histogram-Normality Test	0.724
Heteroscedasticity-Test	0.430

Note: The asterisks ** is 5% significant level. The numbers in parentheses are standard error.

The coefficients of assessed ECM are additionally negative and measurably huge at 5% certainty level. These qualities show that the entire framework change at speed of half (the entire framework can return to since quite a while ago run balance at a speed of half). At the end of the day, these qualities demonstrate that any deviation from the since quite a while ago run harmony between factors is modified for each period to return to the since quite a while ago run balance level.

As appeared in the table, there is no presence for heteroscedasticity or autocorrelation in the residuals of the model over the example time frame. This shows that the aftereffects of the demonstrative tests demonstrates that the model have the ideal econometric properties.

Moreover, because of the underlying changes in Pakistani economy, almost certainly, macroeconomic arrangement might be dependent upon one or numerous primary breaks. Hence, the steadiness of the short-run and the since quite a while ago run coefficients are checked through CUSUM CUSUMSQ tests proposed by Brown et al.(1975). The diagrams speaking to the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 separately.

4.3 Granger Causality Results

As per the outcomes got from the trial of co-joining show that there exist co-mix between factors, so this recommends that there must be Granger causality at any rate one way, however it doesn't demonstrate the course of fleeting causality between the factors. The short run and since quite a while ago run Granger causality are assessed and the outcome can be summed up in table 6.

Table 6: Long-run Granger Causality Results

# of equation	Dependent variable	Long run γ_i
1.	ΔCO_2	-0.369659** (0.099686)
2.	ΔP	-0.003910 (0.201298)
3.	ΔY^2	0.159451 (3.039706)
4.	ΔE	-0.194400*** (0.097704)
5.	ΔD	0.030871 (0.085490)
6	ΔT	0.381134 *** (0.195849)

Notes: *** and ** show that the invalid theory of no causation is dismissed at the 10% and 5% noteworthiness levels, individually. The numbers in enclosures are standard mistakes. Δ is the main distinction administrator. The quantity of proper slack is one as indicated by Akaike data model, Schwarz data standard.

Table 6 sums up the consequences of the since quite a while ago run Granger causality. As indicated by the outcome identified with coefficient on the slacked mistake remedy term, the blunder revision term is factually huge in the carbon emanation condition (#1), so there exists a since quite a while ago run relationship among the GDP, square of GDP, Economic Performance, energy utilization and exchange transparency. This implies that over the long haul, energy utilization, GDP, squared GDP, Economic Performance and unfamiliar exchange Granger-cause CO₂ emissions. This gives the presence of a unidirectional since quite a while ago run causality from per capita GDP, the square of per capita GDP, per capita energy use and Economic Performance to per capita carbon emanations. There exists another since quite a while ago run Granger causality which runs instinctively through the mistake rectification terms from CO₂ emanations, pay, squared pay, Economic Performance and unfamiliar exchange to the energy utilization since the ECT critical in energy condition at 10% degree of huge.

Table 7: Short-run Granger Causality Results

#	Dependent Variable	Δ CO ₂	Δ Y	Δ Y ²	Δ E	Δ F	Δ T
1.	Δ CO ₂	—	-4.502545 (2.995926)	0.304597 (0.198020)	-0.185887 (0.311736)	0.124236 (0.181257)	-0.137596 (0.107358)
2.	Δ P	0.089367 (0.566058)	—	0.468592 (0.434149)	-0.066011 (0.679458)	0.199983 (0.392357)	-0.122877 (0.236246)
3.	Δ Y ²	1.330279 (8.547772)	-106.6809 (99.15357)	—	-0.606514 (10.26017)	3.188689 (5.924791)	-1.811426 (3.567440)
4.	Δ E	0.041264 (0.274747)	-5.165204 (3.187042)	0.348375*** (0.210722)	—	0.251249 (0.190437)	-0.042023 (0.114666)
5.	Δ D	-0.067720 (0.240400)	5.416128*** (2.788625)	-0.351515*** (0.184379)	0.416307 (0.288560)	—	0.013101 (0.100332)
6.	Δ T	-0.390841 (0.550736)	3.747812 (6.388496)	-0.240525 (0.422397)	0.687086 (0.661066)	0.307705 (0.381736)	—

Notes: *** and ** indicate that the null hypothesis of no causation is rejected at the 10% and 5% significance levels, respectively.

Table 7 sums up the aftereffects of short-run Granger causality. With short run impact, per capita GDP, the square of per capita GDP, Economic Performance, energy utilization and Trade are not measurably huge in the carbon discharges. This infers that these factors don't Granger cause per capita carbon emanations in the short-run., the square of per capita GDP is measurably critical, suggesting that the square of per capita GDP Granger cause per capita energy utilization in the short run. In Economic Performance, the per capita GDP, the square of per capita GDP are critical at 10% level. This suggests that these factors Granger cause per capita Economic Performance in the short-run. In entirety, in the short run there is no Granger causality from per capita pay, the per capita pay, Economic Performance, energy utilization, Domestic items and exchange receptiveness to per capita carbon emanation. In any case, there is unidirectional causality from the per capita GDP, the square of per capita GDP to Economic Performance and from the per capita GDP to per capita energy utilization.

The per capita energy utilization is finding that Granger causes per capita carbon outflows over the long haul, however not the other way around. That is, an expansion in energy utilization will help carbon outflows. This suggests that diminishing energy use is a proper method to diminish carbon emanations.

Conclusions

This examination inspects the causal connection between Economic Performance, pay, energy utilization, exchange receptiveness and carbon emanations Pakistan covering the period between 1990 and 2019. The investigation utilizes the time-arrangement information gathered from the World Bank and UNCTAD data sets. The limits F-test for co-joining test yields a proof of a since quite a while ago run connection between per capita carbon discharges, per capita energy utilization, per capita GDP, the square of per capita GDP, Economic Performance and exchange transparency. The outcomes likewise uphold the legitimacy of EKC

speculation in the Pakistani economy, that is, the degree of CO₂ outflows at first expanded with pay, until it accomplished its adjustment point, and afterward it diminished in Pakistan.

The long-run elasticity of CO₂ emanations regarding energy utilization is positive. Besides, the connection between CO₂ discharges and GDP over the long haul is positive, and negative concerning square of GDP. Notwithstanding that, the unfamiliar exchange has positive effect on CO₂ outflows. The discoveries show that Economic Performance has a since quite a while ago run negative effect on per capita CO₂ emissions, recommending that monetary improvement doesn't increment natural corruption, however chips away at upgrading ecological quality by elevating firms to utilize progressed climate amicable strategies. The coefficient of assessed ECT is negative, critical and equivalent 0.50. Causality tests obviously legitimize the since quite a while ago run impacts of energy utilization, GDP, squared GDP, Economic Performance and unfamiliar exchange Granger-cause on CO₂ emanations which clarifies the presence of a unidirectional since a long time ago run causality from per capita GDP, the square of per capita GDP, per capita energy use and Economic Performance to per capita carbon outflows.

Recommendations

In view of the above decisions, the examination suggests various things that should contemplate the climate and its issues to discover approaches to lighten tension on natural assets, given that the climate is the establishment of any continued monetary development along these lines, the investigation suggest:

Decrease of the utilization of contaminating energy, which result from the consuming of oil and its subsidiaries, and utilizing the ecologically amicable sources, for example, wind and sun dependent on the energy utilization result.

The import of creation strategies that are less contaminating to the climate, including the decrease of fuel imports, as it is the fundamental polluter of the climate, and zeroing in on the imports of electric vehicles, and light electric rail rather than conventional dirtying vehicles dependent on the exchange receptiveness result.

Future Directions

The public authority ought to set up light train frameworks, and authorized approaches to decrease deals assessments, customs, and some other expenses for vehicles with little motors dependent on the exchange transparency result.

Urging the monetary area to zero in on improving the nature of the climate through giving them credits that add to the interest in low contamination extends that help in securing the climate and empowering firms in receiving progressed cleaner and climate amicable strategies.

References

- i. Katircioglu, S. T. (2014). *International tourism, energy consumption, and environmental pollution: The case of Turkey*. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 36, 180–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.04.058>
- ii. Kiviyiro, P., & Arminen, H. (2014). *Carbon dioxide emissions, energy consumption, economic growth, and foreign direct investment: Causality analysis for Sub-Saharan Africa*. *Energy*, 74, 595–606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.07.025>
- iii. Kumail, T., Ali, W., Sadiq, F., & Aburumman, A. (2020). *Relationship between CO₂ emissions, tourism receipt, energy use and international trade in Pakistan (2020)*. *Travel and Tourism Research Association: Advancing Tourism Research Globally*. 4. https://scholarworks.umass.edu/ttra/2020/research_papers/4
- iv. Agras, J., and Chapman, D. (1999). "A dynamic approach to the environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis". *Ecological Economics* 28, PP.267–277.
- v. Alkhathlan, K., Javid, M. (2012). "Energy consumption, carbon emissions and economic growth in Saudi Arabia: An aggregate and disaggregate analysis". *Energy Policy* 62, PP.1525-1532.
- vi. Alsaob, N. (2011). "National experiences and the reduction of emissions Jordanian transport sector". *The Ministry of Transport of Jordan*.

- vii. Alwan, K., and Tarawneh, S. (2014). "Mutual effects between economic growth and carbon dioxide emissions in the framework of assumptions Environmental Kuznets curve: a case study of Jordan." *Journal of Jordanian Economic Sciences*, PP. 95-108) In Arabic).
- viii. Ang, J. (2007). "CO2 emissions, energy consumption, and output in France". *EnergyPolicy* 35, PP. 4772–4778.
- ix. Ang, J. (2010). "Research, technological change and financial liberalization in South Korea". *Journal of Macroeconomics* 32, PP.457–468.
- x. Annual Report, 2014. "The Ministry of Industry and Trade and Supply". <http://www.mit.gov.jo/EchoBusV3.0/SystemAssets/PDFs/AR/Publications/%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D9%82%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%B1%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%86%D9%88%D9%8A%202014%20%D8%A2%D8%AE%D8%B1%20%20Copy.pdf>.
- xi. Bahmani-Oskooee, M., and Goswami, G. (2003). "A disaggregated approach test the J-curve phenomenon: Japan versus her major trading partners". *Journal of Economics and Finance* 27, PP.102-113.
- xii. Beckerman, W. (1992). "Economic growth and the environment: whose growth? Whose environment?" *World Development* 20, 481–496.
- xiii. Boutabba, M. (2010). "The impact of financial development, income, energy and trade on carbon emission: Evidence from the Indian economy". *University of Evry-Val d Essonne*, PP. 5-13.
- xiv. Bozkurt, C., and Akan, Y. (2014). "Economic Growth, CO2 Emissions and Energy Consumption: The Turkish Case". *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, PP.484-494.
- xv. Chen, W. (2007). "Economic Growth and the Environment in China". *Annual Conference for Development and Change*.
- xvi. http://www.policyinnovations.org/ideas/policy_library/data/01447/_res/id=sa_File1/paper.pdf, (02.05.2013).
- xvii. Dinda, S. (2004). "Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis: a survey". *Ecological Economics* 49, PP.431–455.
- xviii. Engle, R.F., and Granger, C.W.J. (1987). "Cointegration and error correction representation: estimation and testing". *Econometrica* 55, PP.251–276.
- xix. Fodha, M., and Zaghdoud, O. (2010). "Economic growth and pollutant emissions in Tunisia: an empirical analysis of the Environmental Kuznets Curve". *Energy Policy* 38, PP.1150–1156.
- xx. Frankel, J., and Romer, D. (1999). "Does trade cause growth?" *Am. Econ. Rev.* 89, PP.379–399.
- xxi. Frankel, J., and Rose, A. (2002). "An estimate of the effect of common currencies on trade and income". *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 117 (2), PP.437–466.
- xxii. Grossman, G.M., Krueger, A.B. (1991). "Environmental impacts of the North American Free Trade Agreement". *NBER. Working paper* 3914.
- xxiii. Grossman, G., and Krueger, A. (1995). "Economic environment and the economic growth". *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 110, PP.353–377.
- xxiv. Halicioglu F. (2009). "An econometric study of CO2 emissions, energy consumption, income and foreign trade in Turkey". *Energy Policy* 37 (3), PP.1156–1164.
- xxv. Jalil, A., and Feridun, M. (2011). "The impact of growth, energy and financial development on the environment in China: A cointegration analysis". *Energy Economics* 33, PP. 284–291.
- xxvi. Jalil, A., and Mahmud, S. (2009). "Environment Kuznets curve for CO2 emissions: a cointegration analysis for China". *Energy Policy*, 37, PP.5167–5172.
- xxvii. Jensen, V. (1996). "The pollution haven hypothesis and the industrial flight hypothesis: some perspectives on theory and empirics". *Working Paper 1996.5, Centre for Development and the Environment, University of Oslo*.
- xxviii. Johansen, S., and Juselius, K. (1990). "Maximum likelihood estimation and inference on cointegration – with applications to the demand for money". *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* 52, PP.169–210.
- xxix. Kuznets, P., Simon, P. (1955). "Economic growth and income inequality". *American Economic Review* 45, PP.1–28.
- xxx. Kwiatkowski, D., Phillips, P.C.B., Schmidt, P., and Shin, Y. (1992). "Testing the null hypothesis of stationary against the alternative of a unit root". *Journal of Econometrics* 54, PP.159–178.

- xxxvi. Durbarry, R., & Seetana, B. (2015). Assessing the impact of tourism and travel on climate change. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 24(4), 401–410. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368623.2014.914363>
- xxxvii. Engle, R. F., & Granger, C. W. J. (1987). Co-integration and error correction: Representation, estimation, and testing. *Econometrica*, 55(2), 251–276. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1913236>
- xxxviii. Eyuboglu, S., & Eyuboglu, K. (2019). Tourism development and economic growth: An asymmetric panel causality test. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2019.1588863>
- xxxix. Eyuboglu, K., & Uzar, U. (2019). The impact of tourism on CO2 emission in Turkey. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2019.1636006>
- xl. Fisher, R. A. (1932). *Statistical methods for research workers*. Breakthroughs in Statistics. Springer.
- xli. Haug, A. A. (2002). Temporal aggregation and the power of cointegration tests: A Monte Carlo study. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 64(4), 399–412. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0084.00025>
- xlii. Heidari, H., Katircioğlu, S. T., & Saeidpour, L. (2015). Economic growth, CO2 emissions, and energy consumption in the five ASEAN countries. *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, 64, 785–791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2014.07.081>
- xliii. Jayanthakumaran, K., Verma, R., & Liu, Y. (2012). CO2 emissions, energy consumption, trade and income: A comparative analysis of China and India. *Energy Policy*, 42, 450–460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.12.010>
- xliiii. Johansen, S., & Juselius, K. (1990). Maximum likelihood estimation and inference on cointegration with application to the demand for money. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 52(2), 169–210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0084.1990.mp52002003.x>
- xlv. Jucan, C. N., & Jucan, M. S. (2013). Travel and tourism as a driver of economic recovery. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 6, 81–88. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(13\)00117-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(13)00117-2)
- xlv. Jurdana, D. S., & Frleta, D. S. (2017). Satisfaction as a determinant of tourist expenditure. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 20(7), 691–704. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2016.1175420>